

Simple Considerations for Applying to Graduate School

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The lab recently launched a recruitment campaign for several key positions aimed at addressing critical research areas. These positions included:

1. **Master's Student:** Investigating the diversity of leafhoppers in blueberry fields in Québec, focusing on interactions between leafhoppers, blueberry stunt phytoplasma, and parasitoids.
2. **PhD Student:** Developing smart traps and AI-based tools for real-time identification of leafhoppers.
3. **PhD Student:** Studying phytoplasma effectors in strawberry green petal disease, with a focus on flower development manipulation and leafhopper attractiveness.
4. **Master's Student:** Exploring how different light spectrums contribute to *Clavibacter michiganensis* infection in tomatoes.

These positions were advertised globally and locally to attract a diverse pool of talent. Despite receiving a significant number of applications from international candidates, no applicants were received from Canada, including Québec, which highlights a potential gap in local recruitment efforts.

After reviewing 229 applications to my lab in December 2024, here are a few insights I have gained:

- **Total Applicants:** 229
- **MSc Applicants:** 78
- **PhD Applicants:** 130
- **Countries Represented:** 33

Applicant Distribution by Country: Most applications are from countries in Asia and Africa, such as Pakistan, India, and Nepal. There are no applications from Canada, which is concerning and needs further consideration.

Age Distribution: A significant portion of applicants did not disclose their age. Among those who did, the majority are in their mid-to-late 20s, which aligns with typical postgraduate applicant demographics. While we don't explicitly request this information, many applicants voluntarily provided it.

MSc vs PhD Applications: Most applications were for PhD positions (approximately 62%).

Observations from Application Reviews

While reviewing the applications, several common issues emerged, highlighting areas where candidates could improve to strengthen their chances of success:

1. **Use of Generic or AI-Generated Content:**
 - Some applications included content generated by tools like ChatGPT, often without personalization or context. This resulted in generic statements that failed to convey

genuine interest or understanding of the lab's focus, mission and achievements. I totally support the use of these tools, but consciously (Molligan & Pérez-López et al. 2024).

2. **Incomplete Applications:**

- Missing documents, unclear academic records, and vague details in CVs were frequent issues. These gaps made it difficult to assess candidates' qualifications and fit for the lab. Most importantly, they highlighted a lack of attention to detail—an essential quality we value in applicants.

3. **Lack of Personalization:**

- Many applications lacked tailored statements explaining why the lab's research aligns with the candidate's goals. Candidates often failed to articulate their motivation for applying or how the lab's expertise would benefit their development. This was often a decisive factor in whether an application advanced to the next stage.

These observations motivated the drafting of simple considerations to help students succeed in applications. By providing clear guidance on creating complete, personalized, and compelling applications, students can better position themselves for success in competitive research opportunities.

Some Guidelines for Successful Applications:

1. **Tailor Your Email:**

- Avoid sending generic emails that resemble mass mailings; they are often dismissed.
- Personalize your message for each professor or program by addressing specific aspects of their research that resonate with your academic and career goals.
- Use the PI's correct name and title, and ensure your email is free from spelling and grammatical errors.
- Include a clear subject line that reflects your intent, such as "Prospective Master Student Interested in EdeLab." Some applications lacked clarity on whether the candidate was applying for a Master's or PhD position.

2. **Know Your Audience:**

- Research the PI's recent publications, lab projects, and institutional affiliations before reaching out.
- Review the lab's website (if available) to understand its focus, members, and ongoing work.
- Highlight specific papers or projects that align with your interests and explain their significance to you.
- Mention shared interests or connections to create a personal link and explain why this is the place where you would like to spend the next 2-4 years of your life.

3. **Craft a Comprehensive CV:**

- Organize your CV into clearly labeled sections, such as:
 - **Contact Information:** Your full name, email, phone number, and LinkedIn/website (if applicable).

- **Education:** Include degrees earned, institutions, dates, and notable achievements.
 - **Research Experience:** Describe roles, projects, and key outcomes, without unnecessary details.
 - **Publications and Presentations:** Provide full citations for peer-reviewed articles, conference posters, or talks.
 - **Skills and Certifications:** Highlight technical, laboratory, or software skills relevant to the position.
- Ensure your CV is visually appealing, using professional fonts (e.g., Arial, Times New Roman) and consistent formatting.
 - Avoid overuse of colors, unconventional fonts, or excessive italics, as these can distract from the content.
 - Avoid submitting a one-page CV without sections, as it may lack sufficient detail.

4. **Highlight Academic Performance:**

- Clearly state your GPA for each degree (bachelor's, master's, or PhD, if applicable).
- Provide context to help the reader interpret your scores, such as the grading scale used and the maximum achievable GPA. Different countries (and sometimes regions within a country) use varying grading systems, so clarity is essential.
- If your GPA is not competitive, briefly mention other achievements or experiences that demonstrate your abilities.

5. **Be Honest and Verifiable:**

- Avoid including unverifiable information, such as unconfirmed conference participation or vague claims about skills.
- Ensure all details in your CV and application can be corroborated with evidence, such as certificates, publications, or official documents.
- If you include a narrative style in your cover letter, provide specific examples and references to support your claims. For example: "During my internship, I conducted electrophoresis, which contributed to the publication of Perez-Lopez et al. 2022, where we discovered..."

6. **Take Your Time:**

- Rushing your application can result in avoidable mistakes or missing critical details.
- Submitting earlier does not guarantee better outcomes; focus on the quality of your application.
- Use the full time available before the deadline to refine and proofread your materials.

7. **Submit Legible Documents:**

- Double-check all your application documents for readability and formatting issues.
- Save files as PDFs to ensure formatting is preserved, and name your files appropriately (e.g., "[YourName]_CV.pdf").
- Illegible or poorly formatted documents can undermine an otherwise strong application.

8. **Language Proficiency:**

- Submit language test results (e.g., TOEFL, IELTS) only if explicitly required by the program.

- Demonstrate your willingness to adapt to the cultural and linguistic environment of the country or region where you're applying. For example, mention any efforts to learn the local language or cultural practices.
- Be mindful that not all universities operate in English; showing interest in the primary language of instruction can be advantageous.

9. Write a Strong Cover Letter:

- Use your cover letter to highlight unique aspects of your background and explain how they align with the lab's goals.
- Discuss why you are interested in the lab's specific research topics and how they connect to your long-term objectives.
- Mention what excites you about the city, university, and institute, demonstrating that you've considered the broader environment.
- Conclude with a professional closing that expresses enthusiasm for the opportunity to apply.

10. Understand Diversity Policies:

- Recognize that some PIs or programs may limit the number of trainees from the same country to ensure diversity in their lab.
- If you are aware of this, consider how you can differentiate yourself by emphasizing unique skills or experiences and how you can enrich the group.

11. Avoid Excessive Follow-Ups:

- While it is acceptable to follow up on your application, avoid sending reminders too soon after submitting. Wait at least 2-3 weeks before inquiring or 2-3 weeks after the time the advertising results would be announced.
- Ensure your follow-up email is polite, professional, and adds value by reiterating your interest or sharing updates (e.g., a new publication).
- Persistent or overly frequent follow-ups can be perceived negatively.

By following these guidelines, you can ensure your application reflects your professionalism, preparedness, and suitability for the graduate program or lab you are targeting. Remember, each application is an opportunity to showcase your strengths and aspirations.

Best of luck!

Reference

Joshua Molligan and Edel Pérez-López. Artificial intelligence in academia: opportunities, challenges, and ethical considerations. *Biochemistry and Cell Biology*. e-First <https://doi.org/10.1139/bcb-2024-0216>

Figure 1. Graphic representation of MSc vs PhD applications to EdeLab, Country and age of applicants.

